

RECOGNIZING HOW THE ORGANIZATIONAL COMMUNICATION AND DISTRIBUTIVE JUSTICE TOWARDS ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR IN INTERIOR DESIGN COMPANIES – INDONESIA

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Abstract:

Objectives. The era of globalization has led to increased competition in various industries, with increasing competition, and increasing organizational pressure as competition intensifies, such as lowering operational costs, making workers more productive, and doing things more efficiently. Employees are the most important resource in an organization because they are sources capable of directing, maintaining, and developing the organization in response to the needs of society and the times. Methodology: This research conducts a saturated sample with a total of 161 employees. The analysis was carried out quantitatively with the method of collecting questionnaires. Structural Equation Model (SEM) was used as an analytical method and Smart-PLS was used as an analytical tool. Finding: Distributive justice has no significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior. This is an interesting finding that employees will remain strong as their original attitude even though the opportunity to get a much better achievement is offered to them. Conclusion: Organizational communication has an effect which significant on organizational citizenship behavior. Organizational communication and distributive justice affected significantly organizational commitment. Organizational commitment affected significantly organizational citizenship behavior. Organizational commitment can be mediated by distributive justice to organizational behavior.

Keywords: Organizational communication; distributive justice; organizational citizenship behavior; organizational commitment; Interior Design Companies.

INTRODUCTION

Construction, interior design, and international promotion companies make a major contribution to providing construction and interior design services. Construction activities are the complete or a part of a sequence of making plans or implementation activities along with supervision that consists of work, architectural, civil, electrical, and environmental arrangements, to know construction or different physical form. The interior design company is an experienced business entity working on national projects, as well as the first and largest exhibition of construction, interior design, and Development Company in Indonesia since 1983. The company is the only company of its kind that has an SGS certificate for ISO 9001:2008 in Indonesia. The clients of the company include Unilever, Nestle, Lexus, Jaguar,

Coffee Bean, All world Exhibitions, and others, more than 20 residential designs, 300 interior team members, a one-hectare production facility, and an Interior Design Company helps clients to design and build interior projects together.

According to Soelton et al (2020); Soelton and Nugrahati (2018); employee assets are very crucial in a company because the effectiveness and achievement of the company are very determined by how the performance of human resources in the company. Following the statement of Organ, et, al (2006), OCB is the willingness of employees to take the role (positions) that exceed their main role in a company, so it's better known as extra-role behavior. This Extra- role behavior is also called OCB. Work behavior that exceeds a specific overall performance standard. The extra role has important implications for companies because it refers to the work behavior of employees related to different companies and different co-workers. In addition, the quality of employee over-role behavior affected overall performance and the effectiveness of the company's overall performance. The problem that happened at this Interior design Company is the low attitude of organizational citizenship behavior, including some employees who do not carry out their duties and obligations optimally, that they burden other employees so, that the workload is not balanced. Employees do not have the initiative to replace absent co-workers, some employees arrive late and hinder the course of a job. Some employees don't want to help their co-workers who are overloaded. The last one that becomes the basis of the problem is that employees do not want to stay if the company provides work outside the job-desc, which should be because the rewards are not commensurate.

From the data on a company's revenue, it can be seen that the company's income fluctuates or is unstable. In February and March 2021, the company's revenue decreased by almost 50%, from the revenue in January and April 2021, the company's revenue increased again, before finally, and in May 2021, the company's revenue decreased quite drastically. This income instability occurs because employees tend to work personally or communication is low between employees. As a result, it reduces employee productivity, reduces collaboration between employees, causes poor company performance, and has an impact on decreasing revenue. In the results of the pre-survey, the researcher found the fact that their working hours were not following their employees' work, employees were certainly every day. This is what causes the researcher to conduct research at the Interior Design Company. When employees in an organization have organizational citizenship behavior, they can control themselves and act appropriately for the interests and sustainability of the organization.

Research Gap. This study cites previous studies that provide mixed responses. One of them is the research of Siwi, et.al (2020) "organizational communication has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment". According to Triyanthi and Subudi (2018) that direct organizational communication affected positively and significantly to OCB. Meanwhile, Chasanah (2017) states "distributive justice does not affect organizational commitment". According to Sari (2018) that distributive justice effected significantly affects OCB. Gunawan (2017), said, "That organizational commitment has a significant effect on OCB". Another study by Yuliana et., al. (2018) affected negatively and did not sign the organizational commitment to OCB.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB), following Organ et., al (2006), OCB is the employee's willingness to take roles (positions) that exceed their main role in a company, so it's better known as extra-role behavior. This Extra- role behavior is also called OCB. According to Robbins and Judge (2015), companies that have superior personnel can have higher work performance. Extra-role behavior is work behavior that exceeds specific overall standard performance. Extra role behavior has critical implications for the company because it refers to the work behavior of personnel associated with different companies and co-workers. In addition, the effective mind-set of the extra-role behavior of employees has an effective impact on performance and the effectiveness of the company's standard performance.

Organizational Communication. According to Pace and Faules (2015). Organizational communication is a show and interpretation of messages amid communication units that are part of an organization. According to Syamsudin & Firmansyah (2016), that communication is the process of sending and receiving information or messages between two or more people effectively, so that the intended message can be understood.

Distributive Justice. According to Colquitt (2015), Distributive Justice refers back to the stability of the distribution of organizational effects within side the form of salaries, benefits, and bonuses. When people in the corporation perceive that the ratio of entering rewards they get hold of is balanced, they'll experience fairness which suggests distributive justice. According to Niehoff & Moorman (1993), where there are dimensions and indicators of distributive justice Work Schedules, Salary Levels, Workloads, Awards Received, and job Responsibilities.

Organizational Commitment. Meyer and Allen (1991) Formulate a definition of organizational commitment as a mental assemble this is characteristic of the connection between organizational participants and their companies and has implications for men or woman's selections to hold membership in companies. Based on this definition, it can be concluded that participants who're dedicated to their corporation could be extra capable of surviving as a part of the company than participants who aren't a commitment to the company.

Research Hypothesis and Framework

Organizational communication is how the sender and recipient of diverse organizational messages in formal and casual companies in a company. The larger and extra complicated the company is, the extra complicated the communication process will be. Research conducted by Triyanthi & Subudi (2018) proves the influence amid organizational communication and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. Based on the research above, it can be made the hypothesis which is:

H1: Organizational Communication has a positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

According to Chasanah (2017), Distributive Justice effected positively and significantly to OCB. Iqbal, et al (2012), distributive justice affected positively impacted OCB. Based on the

outcomes of the research above, it could be concluded that the hypothesis on this observation is as follows.

H2: Distributive Justice effected positively to Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

According to Triyanti & Subudi (2018), there is a significant impact of the Organizational Communication variable on Organizational Commitment. According to Siwi, et., al (2020) Organizational Communication has a significant and positive effect on organizational commitment. Based on the effects of the research above, it can be concluded that the hypothesis on this observation is:

H3: Organizational Communication affected positively Organizational Commitment.

According to Sutrisna & Rahyuda (2017) "The Distributive Justice variable affected significantly Organizational Commitment". According to Chasanah (2017), distributive justice has not affected significantly Organizational Commitment. The results of the research above can be concluded the hypothesis is as follows:

H4: Distributive Justice affected positively Organizational Commitment.

According to Priyandini, et al (2020), there is no significant effect of the variable Organizational Commitment on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. According to Gunawan, et al (2012) Organizational commitment has a major impact on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. The research result above can be made the hypothesis as follows:

H5: Organizational Commitment affected positively Organizational Citizenship Behavior

According to Azizah and Prasetyowati (2015), there is a significant positive impact of the variable Organizational Commitment and Organizational Communication on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. According to Putrantoro (2014) that there is a significant positive impact of the variable Organizational Commitment and Organizational Communication on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. Based on the research above, they can be made the hypothesis as follows:

H6: Organizational Commitment can be Mediating Organizational Communication and has a positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

According to Prameswari and Suwandana (2017), Organizational Commitment and Organizational Justice effected positively and significantly to Organizational Citizenship Behavior. According to Sanhaji, et al (2016) that there is an insignificant effect of the variable Organizational Commitment and Distributive justice on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. Based on the research above can be made the hypothesis as follows:

H7: Organizational Commitment can be Mediating Distributive Justice and has a positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Methodology

The research begins by identifying research problems, and formulating and collecting basic theories. Then the researchers prepared the method with data collection, preparation of the instruments, and testing techniques. Considering the population characteristics and the reasons for this research. The sampling Method in this study is a saturated sample, known as the determination of sample in which all participants from the population are used as the sample. This research makes use of a quantitative approach, that the survey is performed with a questionnaire approach that uses PLS – Partial Least Square. The Population of this research is Personnel of the Interior Design Company, 161 Personnel.

Results and Discussion

The Result: pay attention to (R²) R-Square which is the (Goodness of Fit / GoF) tested. Assessing this model using PLS, one begins to observe R² for each assigned latent variable. Following Ghozali (2014), the values of R² are 0.75 indicates strong, 0.50 indicates moderate and 0.25 indicates weak. The relevance of the predicted values (Q-squared) is 0.02 which indicates small, 0.35 which indicates medium, and 0.35 which indicates large. Testing the GOF / Goodness of Fit model used Predictive Relevance (Q²) on the inner model. The value of (Q²/ Q-square) should be more than zero (0), indicating the model has a predictive relevance value.

Table 1: Goodness of Fit Model

Variables	AVE	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha	R-Square
Organizational Communication	0.733	0.965	0.959	–
Distributive Justice	0.703	0.950	0.939	–
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.687	0.968	0.965	0.870
Organizational Commitment	0.658	0.919	0.894	0.767

Source: Processing

Table 2: Result of Hypothesis

	Original Samples	Standard Deviation	T Statistic	P-Values	Description
OC → OCB	0.659	0.072	9.114	0.000	Positive – Significant
DJ → OCB	0.092	0.067	1.377	0.169	Not significant
OC → OCM	0.340	0.090	3.775	0.000	Positive – Significant
DJ → OCM	0.580	0.092	6.274	0.000	Positive – Significant
OC → OCB	0.229	0.080	2.878	0.004	Positive – Significant
Mediation					
OC → OCM → OCB	0.078	0.037	2.094	0.037	Mediated
DJ → OCM → OCB	0.133	0.048	2.759	0.006	Mediated

Source: Processing

Figure 2: Bootstrapping Test Result

Source: Output PLS, 2022

The measurement is to analyze the model to examine the reliability and validity of every dimension also indicator uses to measure each variable that was built previously. The Dimensional model analysis can be defined by explaining the discriminant validity value by examining the square root value of the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) with an encouraging value of more than 0.5 and loading factor of more than 0.5, construction validity also Cronbach Alpha as Composite reliability should be more than 0.70.

The R² (R-square) value indicates a strong creation. So, the proposed model is supported by empirical research where the model is identified as a correct model. Likewise, the AVE value >0.5 indicates that each variable in the model meets the standard of discriminant validity. The value of composite reliability and Cronbach Alpha for each variable is higher than 0.7 (> 0.70), meaning that each variable is categorized as reliable. The measurement results based on the analysis of facts processing at the dimensional model-based indicator show that every one of the indicators processed above in Table 2 is categorized as invalid wherein the majority of the loading issue values are more than > 0.50 (more than 0.50).

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Organizational Communication on Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

Based on the hypothesis, in which are T-statistic is 9,114 and the original sample is 0.659, P-Values is 0.000. The t-Statistic is higher than the T-table value which is 1.96, the original sample value is suggested as effective, and the P-values value is below 0.05, those effects imply that organizational communication has a significant and positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior. Communication occurs between employees, and good communication will also affect the positive behavior of employees as a reflection of organizational citizenship behavior so that employees can obtain, develop and complete the tasks given. On the other hand, if there is poor communication, the result is that there's no good relationship, an authoritarian or detached attitude, differences of opinion or prolonged conflict, and so on, which could affect work results that aren't optimal. Employee communication can form and strengthen the positive attitudes of members as a form of organizational citizenship behavior. This shows that the better communication is carried out by superiors and employees, the organizational citizenship behavior of employees will also be fine.

The Relation of Distributive Justice to Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

Based on the hypothesis are T-statistic is 1.377 and Original Sample is 0.092, P-Values is 0.169. The t-statistic is below the T-table which is 1.96. The Original sample value indicates a positive dan P-value higher than 0.05, these indicate that distributive justice has no significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

This indicates that the size of distributive justice that occurs in the company does not affect the organizational citizenship behavior of its employees. Employees feel that they will continue to do their jobs well despite the unfair conditions in their division of labor. Multiple jobs and the pressure of doing the work, will not increase the organizational citizenship behavior of employees.

The Relation of Organizational Communication to Organizational Commitment.

Based on the result of the Hypothesis, the T-statistic is 3.775, the value of an original sample is 0.340, and P-value is 0.000. The T-statistic is higher than the T-table value is 1.96, the value of the original sample shows positive, and P-value is less than 0.05, which indicates that organizational communication has a significant and positive effect on organizational commitment.

Communication has an important influence, it can even affect employees to be dissatisfied and leave the organization, and namely, their communication tends to decrease. Then positive communication will encourage one's commitment to the organization. Employees who are free to voice their ideas and concerns and get involved in the organization have an impact on the realization of true self-satisfaction, identified with the increased value of commitment to the organization and their work. So that the existence of good communication activities in the organization will affect increasing the commitment of its members.

This result is following the research by Siwi, et., al (2020) which states that organizational communication has a significantly positive effect on organizational commitment.

The Effect of Distributive Justice on Organizational Commitment

Based on the Hypothesis result, the T-statistic is 6.274 and the value of an original sample is 0.580, P-value is 0.000. T-statistic is higher than T-table is 1.96, and the value of the original sample indicates a positive, P-value below 0.05, this result indicates that distributive justice has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. The justice applied by the leadership in the company can increase organizational commitment, including employees feeling fairness in providing workloads, leaders always looking for accurate information when they want to make a decision, leaders treating employees in a good way, leaders treating employees with respect and show concern for when making job decisions. Employees will feel obedient to fair treatment in the organization if the policies, procedures, and practices are fair to all employees. Thus, employees will have confidence in the perceived fairness and be able to increase employee commitment to the organization. This result is following Sutrisna & Rahyuda (2017) who state that there's a significant impact of the distributive justice variable on organizational commitment.

The Relation of Organizational Commitment to Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

Based on the hypothesis result, which is the T-Statistic is 2.878, the value of an original sample is 0.229, P-value is 0.004. The t-statistics value is higher than T-table is 1.96, the value of the original sample indicates a positive value, and P-values below 0.05. This result indicates that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior.

Organizational commitment is a person's strong will to remain in an organization, a willingness that is supported by hard work to match what is expected by the organization, and also a certain belief in accepting the values and achievements of the organization. Thus, for personnel who have got a high commitment to the organization, the employee could be satisfied to do whatever this is believed so that you can develop the organization due to the acceptance as true within the organization so that worker organizational citizenship behavior is formed. This research is in line according to Gunawan, et al (2012) where in his research it shows the variable organizational commitment has a significant effect on the Organizational citizenship behavior variable.

The Effect of Organizational Communication on Organizational Commitment through Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

Based on the hypothesis, the T-statistic value is 2.094 and value of the original sample is 0.078, and P-value is 0.037. The t-statistic is higher than the T-table value is 1.96, and the value of the original sample shows a positive value, P-values below 0.05, this result indicates organizational citizenship behavior can mediate the effect of organizational communication on organizational commitment.

By focusing interest between superiors and subordinates with more incentive communication so that personnel can have an excessive commitment, the effect will arise on the attention of organizational citizenship behavior which also increases. Leaders who provide good communication to their subordinates will be able to increase commitment to their employees. High employee commitment to the company will form positive organizational citizenship behavior so that it can advance the company because it believes in the organization. This research is following Azizah and Prasetyowati's (2015) in their research reveals that there's a significant positive impact of organizational commitment and organizational communication variables on organizational citizenship behavior.

The Effect of Distributive Justice on Organizational Commitment through Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

Based on the hypothesis, the T-statistic is 2.759, the original sample is 0.133, and the P Values are 0.006. The t-statistic is higher than T-table which is 1.96, the original sample value indicates positive, and p-values are less than 0.05, this result indicates organizational citizenship behavior can mediate the effect of distributive justice on organizational commitment.

The condition of distributive justice can be achieved by fulfilling an existing rule or norm. Leaders who can bring up fair environmental conditions both in terms of work placement, workload, and achievement results to employees can lead to a high commitment attitude to their subordinates. Where employees feel that with the creation of a fair work environment they will continue to manifest their loyalty to the company so that the impact will increase organizational citizenship behavior in these personals. The results of this are following Prameswari and Suwandana (2017) who state that there is a significant positive effect of organizational commitment and organizational justice variables on organizational citizenship behavior.

This research is to analyze the variables relates to organizational communication, distributive justice, organizational commitment, and organizational citizenship behavior.

CONCLUSION

The result of this study has been received from studies on personnel of the Interior Design Company. From the results of the calculations in this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- 1) Organizational communication has a significant positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior in Interior Design Company employees. This means that the better the application of corporate organizational communication, the better the organizational citizenship behavior shown by its employees.
- 2) Distributive justice has no significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior in Interior Design Company employees.
- 3) Organizational communication has a significant positive effect on organizational commitment to Interior Design Company employees. This means that if better organizational communication occurs in the company, it will increase employee organizational commitment.
- 4) Distributive justice has a significant positive effect on organizational commitment to Interior Design Company employees. This means that the better the level of distributive justice felt by employees at work, the higher the level of organizational commitment.
- 5) Organizational commitment affected positively and significantly organizational citizenship behavior in Interior Design Company employees. This means that the higher the level of organizational commitment of employees, it will lead to positive organizational citizenship behavior.
- 6) Organizational communication affected positively and significantly organizational commitment through organizational citizenship behavior on Interior Design Company employees.
- 7) Distributive justice affected significantly and positively organizational commitment through organizational citizenship behavior on employees of Interior Design Company.

Based on the results of the research conducted, the suggestion for the company is that Leaders should be able to provide tasks that are by the abilities of employees and be able to provide clear information so that employees can complete tasks by the wishes of the leader, to improve employee organizational citizenship behavior. Leaders should listen to the opinions of employees before making decisions related to work, so that employee organizational citizenship behavior is created properly. Companies are expected to be able to make employees willing to voluntarily do something useful for the company, participate in various activities organized by the company, and be ready to accept the policies set by the company. The creation of employee organizational citizenship behavior must always be maintained by the company's management. Organizational citizenship behavior that is formed will be able to increase organizational commitment from employees. Companies should apply work schedules fairly, leaders must always listen to all employee problems before making decisions, provide opportunities for employees to have opinions on work decisions made by leaders, leaders need to convince employees that someone must be loyal to their organization. The company is expected to improve extra harmonious and comfortable operating surroundings for all

participants of the organization, so that organization participants are expected so it will care about unfinished work among colleagues.

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